

**ON THE PROBLEM OF TRANSLATING THE NAMES OF GARMENTS
IN THE NARRATIVES WRITTEN BY ABDULLA QAHHOR AND
TRANSLATED INTO KOREAN**

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of preserving national color in the translation process and the methods and problems encountered in translating national words. Each method is explained and analyzed with examples from the translation of A. Qahhor's stories into Korean.

Keyword: artistic translation, transliteration, national proper word, reality, transcription, nationality, translation, translation problem, alternative, national color.

In recent years, cultural, social and political relations between Uzbekistan and Korea have improved year by year. This, in turn, creates a basis for the development of linguistic and cultural relations between these two countries. Literary works are directly translated into Korean and Uzbek languages. Unfortunately, some problems in the translation process have not been solved yet. One of these problems is the difficulties in translating realities and the ways to overcome them. It is known that all literature is national in its form and universal in its content. That is, it reflects universal ideas through national means. Therefore, the life of a particular nation is based on an artistic work. Nationality is a set of unique characteristics of each nation, different from others. They can be divided into spiritual activity and peculiarities of material life of one or another nation. Spiritual activity includes people's character, way of thinking, mentality, humor, etc. Material life consists of traditions, customs, ceremonies, clothing, household objects, cuisine, names, etc¹.

¹ Ergash Ochilov. Tarjima nazariyasi. – Toshkent: “Innovatsiya-Ziyo”, 2022, p.150-152.

The article deals with the problem of translation of names of garments in Uzbek stories translated into Korean. The translation of the stories of Abdulla Qahhor into Korean was analyzed.

Analysis of the " Dahshat " story:

Originality: Umsin entered his house, closed the "*paranji*" hood, filled the bucket with water, put tea in the teapot and left².

Korean translation: 운슨은 자신의 방으로 돌아와서 머리에 바란지를 썼다³.

The "*paranji*" is a wide and long "*yoping'ich*"⁴ in the form of a tunic with false sleeves, with which most Muslim women cover their heads in order not to be seen by strange men. Clothing like the burganj does not exist among Koreans, and for this reason the word burganj has been translated by the translator, and the link states that the burganj is a head covering that Uzbek women wear when they go out. Comment on the left. The translator has managed to create an image of our national costume, the burqa, in the mind of the reader, and the translation has been done successfully.

Analysis of the story " To'yda aza ":

Originality: The rumor turned out to be true: the teacher hated to go to the market, to go to the store, someone saw him waiting for him in the department store, and the next day he wore a "*chamandagul do'ppi*" in front of the teahouse⁵.

Korean translation: 소문은 사실이였다. 선생은 장을 보거나 가게에 가는 것을 무척 싫어했다. 그런데 누군가 그가 백화점에서 계산대 앞에 줄을 서

² U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.81.

³ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", 91-bet.

⁴ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. O'zbekiston millioy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.218.

⁵ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.59.

있는 것을 보았다고 했다. 다음 날 선생은 **새 모자를** 쓰고 찾집 앞을 지나갔다⁶.

The ethnic characteristics of each nation are highlighted by an essential component of traditional dress such as headgear. One such headgear is the cap, whose history dates back to ancient times. Images of such headgear can be seen in archaeological finds, frescoes and miniatures. *Do'ppi* is derived from the Turkish word meaning " tepalik ", " cho'qqi ". The hats of different regions differ in colour, decoration and manufacturing techniques. From the hat, one could determine the owner, the region and even the village he came from. In the 1940s, hats from Tashkent are distinguished by their decoration decorated with velvet bushes. Such decoration is called " chamanda gul "⁷.

Chamanda gul doppi, one of our national headgear, is translated as 새 모자 (Se moja) - new headgear. In Chamanda, the flower cap is a foreign concept to the Korean people, and since such headgear does not occur in Korean culture, the translator resorted to the method of substituting words. It should also be noted that the culture of the people is clearly shown in the words specific to the country (realia). Realia are divided into groups with alternatives and without alternatives. Of course, when translating such words, the translator must have a thorough knowledge of Korean culture. It is also not appropriate to conclude that this translation is wrong. However, it should be noted that in many cases, annotations and explanations are used during the translation process to familiarize the reader with the meaning or concept of the words that have been incorporated into the translation through transliteration or transcription. If the translator had translated the word "chamanda gul do'ppi", one of the types of Uzbek headgear, in this way, he would have been able to create an image of the national headgear in the reader's mind.

⁶ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.64.

⁷ <https://tbc-ornaments.uz/ornaments>

Analysis of the story " Yillar ":

Originality: "Yes, we are here," said Orzikul, putting on the sleeve of his "*to'n*"⁸.

Korean translation: 얼주쿨은 옷 소매 속으로 손을 놓으며 계속 말했다⁹.

Long national dress with open front, with or without cotton; is a "*chopon*"¹⁰. In translating the word "*to'n*" in this sentence, the method of generalization is used, using the word *옷 (o't)* to mean the part with the whole. The generalization is the opposite of the concretization¹¹. It should be noted that among Korean national costumes, there was a costume that resembled a tunic in appearance and function, and this costume was called *두루마기 (durumagi)*. The helmet is considered to be the Korean national costume. And this dress was worn by ordinary librarians during the Joseon Dynasty. The sleeves are narrow and straight, the front part is closed with a ribbon on both sides, and the length is 20-25 cm above the ankle¹². "The theory of realistic translation comes to the firm conclusion that the national characteristics reflected in a work must be reflected in the translation, from the point of view that it is a national monument of this or that nation¹³. If we consider this conclusion from the point of view, we come to the conclusion that it is wrong to translate the word "*to'n*" as *두루마기 (durumagi)*, although it is similar in appearance and function. We believe it is correct for the translator to generalize and translate with the word clothing. It is also appropriate to translate or transcribe and leave a comment under the link.

Originality: It is very good, Hajim! You have done a great deal of good. Let them enter. No, no, they will open the "*kovush*" inside¹⁴.

⁸ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.29.

⁹ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.34.

¹⁰ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.235.

¹¹ G'anisher Rahimov. Tarjima nazariyasi va amaliyoti. – Toshkent: "Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti", 2016, p.132.

¹² <https://namu.wiki>.

¹³ Ergash Ochilov. Tarjimashunoslikning nazariy masalalari (o'quv qo'llanma). – Toshkent: "Innovatsiya-Ziyo", 2022, p.155.

¹⁴ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlol", p.29.

Korean translation: 잘하셨습니다, 허지씨. 정말 오랜마니네요. 들어오세요. 아니, **구두**는 방 안에서 벗으시면 됩니다¹⁵.

The word has not found expression in this translation. If "**kovush**" is considered a national shoe, the translator has translated this word with the word **구두**-*tufli*, one of the modern shoes. "**Kavush**" is a shoe made of leather, usually worn with **mahsi**¹⁶. The Korean people also had national shoes that looked like kavush. They were called **태사혜**(*tesakhye*), depending on the shape, in which the ankle was visible, and there were types that covered the ankle. In question are mainly high quality shoes made of silk or leather. Men's and women's shoes differ in their decorative patterns. The shoe decorated with white stripes on the front and heel was intended for men and was called **운혜**(*unhye*). In women's shoes, the front is decorated with a cloud pattern and the heel with a maple tree pattern, and this shoe is called **당혜**(*tanghye*)¹⁷. The question of whether the national characteristics described in the artwork should be retained or changed in the translation-whether they should be transferred to the country where the people of the translated language live-has not yet been finally settled¹⁸. Therefore, the translation of such words poses a number of problems for the translator. In this sentence, too, we see that the translator had difficulties in translating the word **кoвyш**. Although Korean national shoes are similar to the word **kowusu**, we think it is wrong to use the names of these Korean garments in the translation as an alternative to the word **kowusu**. In such a situation, the translator should be able to use all his skills and knowledge to create a national

¹⁵ U. Saidazimova. Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalari. – Toshkent: "Istiqlof", p.35.

¹⁶ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi. – Toshkent: Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, p.290.

¹⁷ <https://m.blog.naver.com/>

¹⁸ Ergash Ochilov. Tarjimashunoslikning nazariy masalalari (o'quv qo'llanma). – Toshkent: "Innovatsiya-Ziyo", 2022, p.155.

identity in the reader's mind. If the translator had left a comment on the link about the kovush, he would have translated it. Tajima would have been successful.

Finally, it should be noted that when translating the work, the translator is obliged to preserve the national color. E. Ochilov, N. Khodjayeva in their book " Tarjima nazariyasi " called the part devoted to the preservation of national color in the translation of the work "Muammolar muammosi". Therefore, when translating a work of a translator, it is especially important to take into account the stylistic and genre characteristics of the text when choosing the method of translation.

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